

Histological basis of resistance in Linseed against bud fly (*Dasyneura lini* Barnes) in Central Uttar Pradesh

*Rishi Pal, Y. P. Malik¹

*F. A. Bio-control Lab, Department of Entomology, S. V. P. University of Agriculture and Technology, Meerut, U.P. India

¹Linseed Unit, Department of Entomology, C. S. A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur, U.P., India

*Corresponding email: rishipal.biocontrol@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on Feb 05, 2020 Revised on March 19, 2020 Accepted on April 01, 2020 Published on April 10, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Rishi Pal, Y. P. Malik Corresponding Author Email rishipal.biocontrol@gmail.com</p>	<p>A field experiment conducted for screened 288 germplasm of linseed against bud fly infestation at Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh during <i>rabi</i> season to study the historical basis of resistance of linseed against bud fly. The results indicated that the sepal thickness negative highly significant relationship ($r=-0.7224$) with bud infestation. The resistant germplasm line maximum sepal thickness (0.49 mm) had relative minimum bud infestation (6.88%) and was statically at par other resistant germplasm lines <i>viz.</i> A-95B, CI-1385, EC-1392, EC-1424, GS-234, IC-15888 and JRF-5. While minimum sepal thickness (0.24 mm) with maximum bud infestation (65.11%) which was statically at par with other susceptible lines <i>viz.</i> Ajan-3-1, Ajan-20M, Alipur (Hamirpur), Anand, GS-148, GS-440, Gunawal Local, NP (RR) 193, RAULD-7810, RLC-28 (PM), MS-14, SJKO-2, SJKO-45. The genotypes with minimum thickness of sepal suffered maximum bud infestation as compared to those with maximum sepal thickness.</p>
PUBLICATION INFO	KEYWORDS
<p>International Journal of Agricultural Invention (IJAI) RNI: UPENG/2016/70091 ISSN: 2456-1797 (P) Vol.: 5, Issue: 1, Pages: 25-30 Journal Homepage URL http://agriinventionjournal.com/ DOI: 10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.3</p>	<p>Linseed, Sepal Thickness, <i>Dasyneura Lini</i>, Bud Fly Infestation, Germplasm, Resistance</p>

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Pal, R., Malik, Y. P. (2020) Histological basis of resistance in Linseed against bud fly (*Dasyneura lini* Barnes) in Central Uttar Pradesh, *International Journal of Agricultural Invention*, 5(1): 25-30. DOI: [10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.3](https://doi.org/10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.3)

Linseed / Flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is being grown since the beginning of civilization and people all over the world have realized its usefulness throughout the ages. The crop has been cultivated for fiber and its seed containing 33-47 % oil content. World over, linseed is an important crop grown over 27.29 lakh ha with production of 25.2 lakh tons with average productivity of 923 kg/ ha, while national production of 1.525 lakh tons is from 3.226 lakh ha with low productivity of 473 kg/ha. However, the remarkable increase in productivity of Rajasthan (1066 kg/ha), Bihar (865 kg/ha) and Nagaland (807 kg/ha) is almost surpassing the productivity of Asia being 524 kg/ha (AICRP, 2013). More than 36 insect-pests are associated with linseed / flaxseed throughout the world, but only a

small number of the major cosmopolitan insect-pests cause economic yield loss to this crop (Malik, 1998). However, yield losses due to bud fly (*D. lini*) have been reported ranging between 17-49% with an average of 40 % at national level (Malik, 2006). Such heavy losses in seed yield due to bud fly incidence can be reduced up to some extent by manipulations in agronomic practices (Singh *et al.*, 1991, Malik *et al.*, 1996, Malik *et al.*, 1999, Malik *et al.*, 2000 and Malik *et al.*, 2008) but the successful management of this pest by the use of systemic insecticides is quite easy, encouraging and cost effective especially in late sown crop (Jahkmola *et al.*, 1973, Sood and Pathak, 1984, Malik 1998 and Malik *et al.*, 2012).

The resistant varieties are one of the fundamental, widely accepted and eco-friendly tools of integrated pest management (IPM) according to (Painter, 1951) and Panda and (Khush, 1995). Each plant species possessed unique defense mechanism involving various histological traits which have deep effect on the reproduction and survival of insect pests on a plant species. Therefore, present study was undertaken for various detailed studies to pin point the resistance mechanism involved in resistant lines with histological parameter. These resistant or tolerant lines may prove safer to natural enemies and ultimately to the whole ecosystem.

Materials and Methods

A set of 288 elite germplasm of linseed was obtained from Project Coordinating and Germplasm Management Unit (Linseed) of this university and evaluated for elite germplasm of linseed was sown paired rows of test entries of 3 m length at 30 cm row distance their reaction to bud fly (*D. lini*) under natural field conditions were carried out at Oilseed Research Farm Kalyanpur, C. S. A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur during *rabi* 2012-13. This trail was executed in Augmented Block Design consisting 18 blocks of 16 test entries in each block. Two checks *i.e.* Neela (Resistant check) and Neelum (SC) were also planted in each block. The crop was sown in the mid of November.

The bud fly infestation was recorded at dough stage on five plants per entry by counting total number of floral buds as well as bud fly infested buds, which was statistically converted into per cent bud infestation. The germplasm were grouped into resistant, moderately resistant, moderately susceptible, susceptible and highly susceptible on the basis of Bud fly Infestation Index (B.I.I.) as suggested by (Malik, 2005). The sepal thicknesses were measured by digital instruments.

Results and Discussion

Sepal thickness in linseed flower buds ranged between 0.24mm (SJKO-45) to 0.50 (Pusa-9). Like-wise the flower dimension, the sepal thickness was also grouped into three categories *i.e.* thin (>0.24 to 0.32 mm), normal (>0.32 to 0.40 mm) and thick (>0.40mm).

Based on the classification, a number of 81, 163 and 44 genotypes of linseed were observed having thin, normal and thick sepals of the flower buds, respectively. This character of flower buds was found as desirable traits, as such germplasm lines were least infested by the bud fly. It is worth explaining that the resistant genotypes *viz.* A-95B, CI-1385, EC-1392, EC-1424, GS-234, IC-15888, JRF-4 and JRF-5 exhibited up to 10% bud infestation due to bud fly *D. lini* were having these entries consisted thinner sepals showing 0.35 to 0.49 mm thickness.

The correlation study showed that there was a highly negative significant correlation ($r=-0.7224$) between thickness of sepals and bud infestation. It showed that germplasm with thick sepal indicate resistance to bud fly attack. From the above results, it was clear that as the sepal thickness increases, infestation by *D. lini* decreases. While considering the thickness of sepals in two hundred eighty and eight lines of germplasm under test was a highly significant negative correlation ($r=-0.7224$) between thickness and % bud infestation. These types of thicker flower buds were measured with highest sepal thickness. Genotypes like Jabalpur-1986, 333-6, A-44, EC-1424, EC-99090, EC-41618, IC-15888 and RL-2600 were having 7.98 to 9.52 mm length and 3.42 to 4.08 mm width, which showed thicker sepal measuring 0.30 to 0.48 mm.

Malik *et al.* (1995) reported that bud fly susceptible line *i.e.* Neelum had maximum sepal thickness, while, resistant line *i.e.* Neela had minimum sepal thickness. Correlation between bud fly infestation and sepal thickness also studied by (Malik *et al.*, 1995) observed significant positive impact between them. This finding is contradictory with the present finding correlation study was a highly significant negative correlation ($r= -0.699$) between thickness of sepals and % bud infestation.

Similarly, (Sood and Pathak, 1990) reported that variety JLS (J) with maximum thickness (45.24 μ) of sepals suffered minimum bud infestation (7.82 %) and variety LC 122 with minimum thickness (23.02 μ) of sepals suffered maximum with bud infestation (38.10 %). The relationship of the thickness of sepals with % bud infestation showed a perfect correlation.

This clearly brought out that with the increase in thickness of sepals, there was a proportionate decrease in the extent of infestation. These findings were in agreement with those of (Painter, 1951) who reported that thickness of plant parts is an important component when insect plant interaction factors for plant resistance are considered. Sepal is the only egg laying site of bud fly in linseed bud. Female fly probably find difficult to penetrate the ovipositor in to the full thickness of sepals.

Host-plant selection theory based on the principle that female prefers the plant /plant part for egg laying where its progeny will survive and develop. In host-plant selection theory (Thorsteinson, 1958) clearly indicated that insect female has strong instinct as parental care. Host-plant relationship work has been done by (Agrawal, 1969) in sugarcane and reported that the stem thickness was associated with the resistance to the sugarcane borer *Diatracea saccharalis* Fabricius.

Acknowledgements

Authors are grateful to Dr. Y. P. Malik Associate Professor, Entomology (Linseed Unit) necessary facilities under Project Coordinating Unit (Linseed) C. S. A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Summery

Two hundred eighty and eight germplasm /varieties of linseed genotypes during *rabi* season were screened on the basis sepal thickness against bud fly infestation. The minimum thickness of sepal suffered maximum bud infestation as compared to those small bud structures with maximum sepal thickness.

Fig 1. Sepal thickness and bud fly infestation linseed germplasm during Rabi season

Table 1. Sepal thickness and bud fly infestation of linseed germplasm during Rabi season

S. N.	Entry	Sepal Thickness	Bud Fly Infestation%	S. N.	Entry	Sepal Thickness	Bud Fly Infestation%	S. N.	Entry	Sepal Thickness	Bud Fly Infestation%
	Neela (Check-1)	0.37	14.5						Neelum (Check-2)	0.32	38.87
1	1/76	0.42	10.61	97	CI-2205	0.34	15.24	193	Polf-17	0.38	44.30
2	3/1	0.48	11.63	98	CI-2206	0.38	19.50	194	Polf-30	0.42	19.50
3	5/47	0.46	12.45	99	Detal-1	0.40	23.98	195	Pusa-9	0.50	12.14
4	5/47-2/1-10/10	0.44	22.42	100	EC-100	0.36	18.67	196	R-966-5	0.38	28.03
5	9 × 17	0.36	26.76	101	EC-519K	0.36	19.44	197	RAULD-19	0.30	26.70
6	9 × JBP-1986	0.28	38.88	102	EC-534	0.34	15.51	198	RAULD-7810	0.34	60.44
7	Jabalpur- 1986	0.26	38.63	103	EC-536	0.36	18.78	199	RL-8-1	0.36	33.88
8	11 × 13	0.34	30.08	104	EC-561	0.36	14.50	200	RL-58-3	0.38	48.55
9	11 × 17	0.34	35.58	105	EC-650	0.34	13.49	201	RLC-22	0.44	14.50
10	12 × 15	0.30	36.58	106	EC-1222A	0.38	16.60	202	RLC-28 (PM)	0.36	52.55
11	18 × B-1	0.38	11.75	107	EC-1392	0.46	18.70	203	RLC-36	0.32	28.90
12	19-1-62	0.38	29.35	108	EC-1394	0.46	11.34	204	RLC-38	0.40	23.00
13	23/3	0.44	11.89	109	EC-1409A	0.26	33.50	205	RLC-53	0.44	19.80
14	39-1	0.46	15.80	110	EC-1409B	0.28	32.24	206	R-204 × No.-55-32	0.38	16.77
15	88-LHCK-7	0.36	15.69	111	EC-1411	0.38	16.56	207	Rajim-2	0.40	25.67
16	149-T-126-1	0.28	39.76	112	EC-1411CS	0.36	24.50	208	Redwing	0.42	11.99
17	162-OR-3-1	0.39	26.37	113	EC-1424	0.48	7.07	209	S-91-24	0.35	16.17
18	333-6	0.3	43.35	114	EC-1918	0.28	40.46	210	S-91-29	0.35	28.45
19	473	0.33	32.47	115	EC-1977	0.34	17.75	211	S-91-49	0.37	68.80
20	474-3/2	0.41	17.45	116	EC-99080	0.32	38.45	212	S-91-55	0.33	48.70
21	477-3/2	0.39	15.49	117	EC-10663	0.30	43.40	213	S-165-13	0.35	35.89
22	1491	0.37	18.88	118	EC-14546	0.41	18.12	214	S-801	0.41	11.44
23	1541	0.39	18.65	119	EC-22481	0.41	11.34	215	Sirmor-2	0.33	42.65
24	1937	0.33	38.89	120	EC-22909	0.34	37.61	216	T-56	0.31	47.10
25	A-3-1	0.31	35.45	121	EC-41404	0.36	32.65	217	T-126	0.29	49.50
26	A-4-3-1-13	0.30	49.47	122	EC-41561	0.32	18.77	218	Tikamgarh	0.49	10.63
27	A-12-1-2	0.37	26.66	123	EC-41564	0.38	16.78	219	UP-6	0.39	28.78
28	A-15-1-2	0.41	14.77	124	EC-41589	0.30	36.78	220	BAU-610A	0.47	12.90
29	A-43	0.29	45.59	125	EC-41609	0.42	12.10	221	DPL-17	0.33	34.88
30	A-44	0.29	69.99	126	EC-41618	0.40	16.58	222	DPL-19	0.41	13.11
31	A-52	0.41	18.40	127	EC-41622	0.38	18.89	223	LC-2198	0.43	28.60
32	A-59	0.31	32.65	128	EC-41635	0.4	15.44	224	RL-56-6-2	0.45	20.44
33	A-62	0.36	16.53	129	EC-41984	0.30	29.88	225	RL-906	0.39	12.22
34	A-76	0.36	14.57	130	EC-50089	0.36	16.78	226	RL-966	0.35	29.80
35	A-84	0.34	15.33	131	EC-99009	0.28	38.77	227	RLC-27	0.37	16.77
36	A-95	0.25	38.85	132	EC-110286	0.36	14.22	228	RLC-53	0.30	26.55
37	A-95B	0.44	6.55	133	EC-110289	0.36	18.40	229	OR-3-1	0.37	13.34
38	A-100	0.28	39.70	134	EC-1534	0.38	19.75	230	MS-1	0.26	48.88
39	A-131	0.26	33.88	135	EC-14600	0.40	11.50	231	MS-14	0.27	56.90
40	A-132	0.28	38.44	136	EX-131-10	0.28	25.75	232	BSL-10	0.33	50.40
41	A-170	0.32	28.45	137	Flax-16	0.30	38.78	233	BSL-12	0.25	55.70
42	A-171	0.30	35.87	138	FR-3	0.34	29.45	234	FRW-1	0.33	47.45
43	A-180	0.36	14.75	139	FX-16	0.48	11.40	235	KSY-1	0.37	34.90
44	A-198	0.25	48.56	140	Gewargi-1-2	0.32	45.44	236	KYS-2	0.35	36.45
45	A-223-B	0.26	30.78	141	GS-27	0.36	12.55	237	NP (RR)-45	0.35	12.55
46	A-308	0.28	48.11	142	GS-39	0.31	38.43	238	NP (RR)-485	0.37	18.25
47	A-370	0.30	39.44	143	GS-40	0.32	35.80	239	A-6-1-2	0.37	28.35
48	A-391A	0.28	28.50	144	GS-41	0.30	44.20	240	EC-22648	0.37	14.70
49	A-405	0.30	26.78	145	GS-109	0.39	16.33	241	EC-22680	0.28	18.60
50	A-411	0.34	29.55	146	GS-121	0.31	47.88	242	EC-41593	0.34	40.80
51	A-416	0.36	24.89	147	GS-148	0.29	55.78	243	EC-282801	0.32	16.06
52	A-419	0.36	18.70	148	GS-150	0.39	16.45	244	EC-282869	0.34	16.51
53	A-426	0.28	38.45	149	GS-203	0.37	16.56	245	EC-312953	0.32	32.77
54	A-440B	0.30	35.34	150	GS-226	0.35	13.77	246	EC-322640	0.28	18.66

55	A-447	0.36	28.67	151	GS-234	0.49	6.88	247	EC-322641	0.34	10.30
56	A-449	0.38	15.89	152	GS-253	0.33	23.44	248	EC-322651	0.36	24.65
57	Ajgan-3-1	0.29	55.45	153	GS-268	0.37	15.89	249	EC-322654	0.28	23.25
58	Ajgan-7	0.34	49.23	154	GS-288	0.41	16.10	250	EC-322655	0.30	14.56
59	Ajgan-20M	0.26	58.80	155	GS-344	0.35	19.23	251	EC-322656	0.30	13.77
60	Alipur(Hamirpur)	0.27	55.06	156	GS-415	0.30	48.88	252	EC-322661	0.38	22.88
61	Alipur(Hamirpur-2)	0.36	18.90	157	GS-440	0.31	55.23	253	EC-322680	0.38	14.50
62	Anand	0.27	58.67	158	Gulberga-1-2	0.39	25.90	254	EC-399582	0.40	18.89
63	Army		65.11	159	Gunawal		60.55	255	SJKO-2		54.55
		0.24			Local	0.27				0.26	
64	Ayogi	0.28	42.45	160	H-11	0.33	38.88	256	SJKO-11	0.38	11.89
65	BAU-154	0.34	38.66	161	H-15	0.34	24.25	257	SJKO-12	0.39	12.25
66	BR-5	0.29	34.78	162	H-22	0.40	12.89	258	SJKO-14	0.33	26.90
67	BR-25	0.39	23.67	163	H-23	0.36	13.50	259	SJKO-17	0.35	12.66
68	BS-1	0.39	12.88	164	H-25	0.34	23.88	260	SJKO-19	0.39	12.40
69	BS-18	0.31	48.65	165	H-31	0.36	18.88	261	SJKO-20	0.37	10.57
70	BS-30	0.39	23.56	166	H-42	0.46	10.88	262	SJKO-27	0.31	38.25
71	Bachhlone Sagar	0.31	38.45	167	I/276	0.40	19.70	263	SJKO-34	0.29	45.67
72	Bengal-62	0.37	14.65	168	IC-15888	0.48	8.34	264	SJKO43	0.25	44.20
73	Bijapur	0.35	19.45	169	JBP Stray-II	0.40	34.60	265	SJKO-45	0.24	61.80
74	Balley Garden	0.37	26.89	170	JRF-4	0.45	3.44	266	SJKO-46	0.37	12.50
75	C-5-82	0.28	47.35	171	JRF-5	0.48	7.43	267	BRM-1	0.33	22.75
76	CC-1-2	0.39	14.30	172	KL-1	0.30	42.55	268	BRM-2	0.31	18.88
77	CI-244	0.33	36.67	173	L-40	0.38	15.50	269	BRM-4	0.33	36.70
78	CI-808	0.39	16.87	174	L-59	0.46	10.00	270	RSJ-9	0.29	23.90
79	CI-1385	0.49	9.80	175	L-70	0.38	14.50	271	RSJ-14	0.28	34.70
80	CI-1427	0.39	16.44	176	L-93	0.40	9.45	272	RSJ-34	0.29	18.67
81	CI-1459	0.39	24.23	177	NO-10	0.33	39.02	273	KL-213	0.30	44.65
82	CI-1539		16.45	178	NO -18 × RR-9		38.20	274	KL-214		47.90
		0.47				0.30				0.32	
83	CI-1612	0.39	16.89	179	NP-23	0.33	40.60	275	KL-218	0.38	13.25
84	CI-1696	0.39	18.57	180	NP-23K	0.34	35.55	276	KL-219	0.38	18.20
85	CI-1897	0.41	11.34	181	NP-24	0.23	48.34	277	KL-231	0.30	44.60
86	CI-1956	0.41	26.85	182	NP-94	0.33	43.55	278	OLC-40	0.28	45.70
87	CI-1983	0.33	38.55	183	NP (Hyb)-23	0.39	19.44	279	RKY-6	0.32	49.90
88	CI-1984	0.35	14.50	184	NP (Hyb)-61	0.37	12.78	280	RJK-7	0.38	16.88
89	CI-2007	0.39	24.67	185	NP (RR)-68-R	0.41	17.20	281	RJK-36	0.30	38.33
90	CI-2048	0.35	21.50	186	NP (RR)-193	0.29	55.44	282	LCK-4036	0.40	22.80
91	CI-2049	0.39	14.5 4	187	NP (RR)-204	0.45	16.89	283	RLC-106	0.40	15.66
92	CI-2052	0.39	19.89	188	NP (RR)-247	0.33	38.50	284	PCL-12-3-06	0.36	10.55
93	CI-2060	0.43	18.92	189	NP (RR)-268	0.39	19.99	285	LBR-6	0.36	13.55
94	CI-2066	0.41	29.11	190	NP (RR)-402	0.45	15.40	286	SLS-77	0.40	11.14
95	CI-2201	0.43	19.65	191	Pink Petal	0.37	48.65	287	RL-2600	0.40	15.44
96	CI-2204	0.39	23.78	192	Polf-12	0.35	28.34	288	PKDL-94	0.28	48.44

Sepal thickness Correlation coefficient (r=-0.7224)

General Mean (Original)		Sepal Thickness (mm)	
		0.36	27.33
Range (Original)	Minimum	0.24	3.44
	Maximum	0.50	69.99
Comparison			
Check vs Check	SE (d)	0.01	0.90
	CD	0.03***	3.55***
Varieties with in same block	SE (d)	0.03	3.80
	C D	0.12***	15.07***
Varieties in different blocks	SE (d)	0.04	4.66
	C D	0.14***	18.46***
Checks vs Varieties	SE (d)	0.03	3.38
	C D	0.08**	NS

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